

Management Concept of Integrated Border Areas Through Regional Regulatory Product in Sambas Regency

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 02, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 22, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Local regulation, Integrated, Border Area</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4781360</p>	<p><i>The border areas between countries in Indonesia are faced important problems caused by the clash of management authorities, poverty, development disparities, technological mastery gaps. The promising potential of natural resources is not fully maximized. This condition reflects the need for responsive and progressive local regulations to anticipate the problems that occur. The commitment of the Regional Government is a priority to build a prosperous and socially equitable border area for the community. The border area in Sambas Regency requires products from Regional Regulations which can contain integrated border area management values, especially concerning the authority for border management which does not only emphasize infrastructure and physical development, but also must be considered the level of welfare of border communities. The policies and development carried out by the Central Government will not be able to be felt in the border area as long as the Regional Government has not been able to translate it into the local regulation order.</i></p>

Introduction

Whereas protected forest areas along the Sajingan Besar District and Paloh District are inhabited by Dayak people from generation to generation. It was also added that in the Sajingan Besar sub-district a national cross-lane road had been opened connecting the Sambas City area to the border in Aruk Village. The Regional Government Law mandates the central government and governor to coordinate with the regent / mayor in carrying out border development affairs. However, in fact, in some sectors, border development affairs are not coordinated further between the central government and the district / city government. Even the provincial government took over all matters related to forestry management while the monitoring and evaluation were submitted to the Sambas Regency government. Then, the problem that arises is the division of authority between the central government, the government of the Province of West Kalimantan, and the Government of the Regency of Sambas is unclear.

This inhibited further coordination related to technical matters that must be developed by the Sambas Government. One of the coordination barriers relates to investors. The lack of clarity of regulation certainly inhibits the investment income in the Regency which has a direct impact on the opportunity to increase Sambas Regency's Original Regional Income (PAD). So far, border management is coordinated under the auspices of the National Border Management Agency (BNPB) under the coordination umbrella of the Ministry of Home Affairs. BNPB as a central state institution that functions to coordinate, integrate, synergize, and synchronize plans from various business sectors and the community in managing the borders of the country and bordering regions based on the time frame, location, funding sources, and those responsible for implementation. BNPB is tasked with designing and providing information on the master plan for managing national borders for the next 5 (five) years.

In the analysis of the results of monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the BNPP program for the period 2011-2014 it was stated that the problems that emerged in the land border area were not far from the issue of infrastructure, not optimal immigration, customs and security and quarantine posts, administrative and health services, education, and optimization management of natural resources and human resources that are not optimal. So that the problems experienced by the District of Sajingan Besar have represented the problems of land border areas in other regions. Based on the descriptions above, the important thing needed to optimize the potential of border management is the clarity of regulations for the management of border areas by Sambas Regency in terms of the construction of infrastructure, social culture, economy, health, and human resources.

Research problem

The existing condition has given birth to the main question concerning the issue of how the existing regional government policy products are related to the management of border areas in Sambas Regency and what is the direction of the Sambas Regional Government policy in managing border areas.

Theoretical reviews

The commitment built by the founding father agreed that the state is formed based on the principle of law (*rechstaat*), not a state based on power (*machtstaat*). Through this agreement, all activities of people's lives can be explored in the process must be based on the rules of law that have been formulated together, even though the Rule of Law has not been properly enforced (Hartono, 1982, p. 54). This rule of law is not an issue that can be "taken lightly", on the contrary the Rule of Law issue affects the entire life of the community, as the life of the community itself also greatly influences the law enforcement of the Rule of Law (Licht, Goldschmidt & Schwartz, 2007).

The aim of the establishment of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia in the Opening of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, as one of the policies of the law of the State of Indonesia, among others, is "advancing public welfare". In order to advance the general welfare, the relationship between Indonesian people and their land is carried out and summarized in the provisions of Article 33 paragraph (3) of the 1945 Republic of Indonesia Constitution which affirms the basic policy regarding the control and use of existing natural resources, with the words:

"Earth and water and the natural wealth contained in them are controlled by the State, and are used for the greatest prosperity of the people".

But both in the body and in the explanation of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, there was no explanation regarding the nature and scope of the control rights of the state, which included the earth and water, and the natural wealth contained therein. In the explanation of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia the affirmation was only given, that the earth and water and natural resources contained in the earth are the main points of people's prosperity, because that must be controlled by the state and used for the greatest prosperity of the people.

The Regional Government must be able to realize a product of legal norms that can become a guarantee for efforts to improve the welfare of the community. The formulated value order must rest on the primacy of the values that lead to the concept of sustainable development (Hardjasoemantri, 2017). People often forget, there is a very close relationship between national integration, economic recovery and law enforcement. Countries that can guarantee good economic growth and national integration are those who carry out law enforcement very well (Himawan, 2003, pp. 91–92).

The core legal system seeks to have the task of safeguarding the interests that exist in the growth of the development of competing communities, for which factors are needed, namely stability through a state that is safe for law to play a role in motion the dynamics of community development, the condition of being able to predict changes that occur, the existence of honesty values in development activities, educational aspects and the ability of the legal profession to anticipate problems arising from changes in development (Himawan, 2017).

The legal function in the economic field is to ensure economic stability and certainty, namely to organize mechanisms and interactions between communities or between economic actors in utilizing limited economic resources. In another perspective development is one way to be able to spur economic growth, and one of the development systems that has an influence on society is by developing the regional economy with the Regional Autonomy system. We are fully aware that in most areas of people's lives now normalization of human behavior has been carried out so that the law covers all fields.

Penetration of law into a society that is so thick can result in demands to make changes and the development of the law itself and its relation to other social problems will also become more intensive (Sutrisno, 2009, p. 56). Thus social problems must be dealt with extraordinarily by law and must work extraordinarily (Sutrisno, 2014). The starting point of this thinking is based on the commitment of the legal state that the state is based on law, namely that all state activities should be based on law (Yasin, 2014). This is closely related to the 4 (four) legal models, namely, *first*, the very repressive model of colonial law; *second*, the legal development model; *third*, a progressive legal model; and *fourth*, the integrative legal model (Atmasasmita, 2012).

Method

This study uses a non-doctrinal legal research approach with the consideration of achieving the ultimate goal of synchronization and harmonizing and reconstructing legal product regulations in the border area in the form of PERDA with national regulations as stipulated through legal products of Law Number 23 of 2014, Law Number 12 of 2011 and Law Number 32 of 2009 as well as reconstruct regulations in the Sambas border area based on the values of local wisdom that were born and developed from the lives of people on the Sambas border, starting

from the two perspectives that are to be researched and developed, research methods are used non-doctrinal law which is focused on two aspects, namely normative aspects and sociological aspects.

The understanding in this study is based on the values, legal principles and applicable legal basis as the product of the legislation described above and the sociological review described above, which in the end the Sambas District Government in West Kalimantan must be able to build products regional policy (policy) which has more content accommodates the importance of the application of local wisdom values, this is an alternative to synergizing regional arrangements as an alternative in implementing sustainable development strategy policies. The importance of juridical-sociology studies with the consideration of pragmatic mindset of the policy holders in the region and the philosophical side of values in the area in this case the Sambas border area, to examine the entire regulation in the context of fulfilling the needs of an applicable legal rule inventory which can finally be avoided overlapping regulations and implementing regulations in the regions.

Synchronization of regulations and harmonization of legal provisions with values and culture in society that apply as one of the objectives to be achieved from a juridical sociology research approach. This is also closely related to the existence of legal rules that exist in the border areas of West Kalimantan which are geographically adjacent to allied countries, namely Malaysia. Malay cultural closeness is a challenge for the Regional Government of Sambas Regency in formulating the value order as outlined in the Regional Regulation legal product.

Law can be learned both from the perspective of law or social sciences, or a combination between the two. Socio-legal studies are studies of law using the approach of law and social sciences. *First, Legal research* is a textual study, articles in legislation and policies can be analyzed critically and explained the meaning and implications for legal subjects (including marginalized groups). In this case it can be explained how the meaning contained in these articles. Therefore *socio-legal* studies also deal with the heart of the problem in legal studies, namely discussing the constitution to the lowest level of legislation such as Village Regulations (Irianto, 2013, pp. 177-178).

Second, socio-research namely legal studies requires an interdisciplinary approach, namely concepts and theories from various disciplines combined and combined to examine legal phenomena, which are not isolated from social, political, economic, cultural contexts, where the law is located (Irianto, 2013, p. 174). Quoting the opinion of Wheeler and Thomas, socio-legal studies are an alternative approach that tests doctrinal studies of law. The word "socio" in socio-legal studies represents the context in which law exists (*an interface within a law exists*) (Banakar & Travers, 2005). By Brian Z. Tamanaha it is said that law and society have a frame called "The Law Society Framework" which has certain relationship characteristics. This relationship is indicated by two basic components. The first component consists of two main themes, namely the idea that law is a mirror of society and the idea that the function of law is to maintain "social order". The second component consists of three elements, namely custom / consent, morality / reason, and positive law. Custom / consent and morality / reason can be understood in Donald Black's thinking as a culture (Banakar & Travers, 2005).

Results and Discussion

The decentralization policy that is the spirit of regional autonomy is expected to provide more opportunities for democratic changes in the life of the Regional Government to bring the government closer to the people. The essence of democracy is the involvement of the people both in the administration of government, development and public services and in exercising control over what the government is and will do.

Regional development as an integral part of national development cannot be forced from the principle of Regional Autonomy, as autonomous regions have the authority and responsibility to carry out community interests based on the principles of openness, community participation and accountability to the community (Widjaja, 2002, p. 2-3).

Based on Article 1 point 6 of Act Number 23 of 2014 on Regional Government, Regional Autonomy is the right, authority and obligation of autonomous regions to regulate and manage Government Affairs and the interests of the local community in the system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. There are several problems that disrupt the implementation of autonomy in a very basic area, including a number of things. *First*, the implementation of Regional Autonomy by the Central Government has tended not to be considered as a constitutional mandate so that the decentralization process was hampered. *Second*, the strong centralization policy in certain fields in the administration of government and everything related to it, made the dependence of regions to the center increasingly high which almost killed the creativity of the community along with all government apparatus in the region. *Third*, there is a wide gap between the region and the center and between the regions themselves in the ownership of natural resources, cultural resources, economic infrastructure and the level of quality of human resources. *Fourth*, there are interests inherent in various parties that hinder the implementation of Regional Autonomy.

The principle of implementing Regional Autonomy certainly on the one hand raises the optimism of the implications for improving services, empowerment and participation of regional communities and fosters regional competitiveness in realizing the welfare of regional communities by taking into account the principles of democracy, equity and specialties of a region. On the other hand, it is also necessary to pay attention to several aspects of vulnerability which could be a negative side of the implications of Regional Autonomy if the spirit and main objectives of Regional Autonomy are only placed solely as regional freedom to look for regional (financial) income sources (Sitompul & Lubis, 2017).

Local Government governance must ultimately be able to act in the realm of realizing the concept of good governance with principles that must be agreed upon by stakeholders in the region. This is important by reasoning the application of the principles of good governance is expected to be able to build regional regulations that work in synergy with the concept of sustainable development strategies, the principles of good governance, namely community participation, rule of law, transparency, care for stakeholders including the business world, consensus oriented, equity, effectiveness and efficiency, accountability, and strategic vision so that ultimately the policy of the Regional Government is fully built able to side with the interests of the community to build prosperity and on the other hand the alignment of wisdom in the environment is not neglected.

Regional governments in border areas must be able to realize regulations that have more specific and distinctive abilities to respond to the needs of the people in the border region given that the condition of the border region is believed to have a social problem that is very different from in other regions not in the border with other countries. Regarding this matter even though in Act Number 23 of 2014 on Regional Government (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2014 Number 244), Article 236 regulates in paragraph (1) to carry out Regional Autonomy and Assistance Tasks, Regions form a Regional Regulation. Whereas Paragraph (2) of the Regional Regulation as referred to in paragraph (1) is formed by the DPRD with the agreement of the head of the Region. And Paragraph (3) of the Regional Regulations as referred to in paragraph (1) contain load material: a. implementation of Regional Autonomy and Assistance Tasks; and b. further elaboration of the provisions of higher laws and regulations. And paragraph (4) In addition to the content material as referred to in paragraph (3) the Regional Regulation can contain local content material in accordance with the provisions of the legislation.

Based on the provisions of Act Number 12 of 2011 on the Establishment of Legislation, Article 1 number 7 that the Provincial Regional Regulation is a Legislation that is formed by the Provincial Regional Representative Council with the agreement of the Governor. Furthermore, in number 8, the Regency / City Regional Regulation is a Legislation that is formed by the Regency / City Regional Representative Council with the agreement of the Regent / Mayor. Based on these legal norms that authority is imposed on the Regional Government, more specifically the Regional Government in the West Kalimantan border region of Sambas Regency must be responsive given the existence of local wisdom values that grow in border communities with Malaysia.

The Regional Government must also be able to understand Law Number 23 Year 2014: CHAPTER XIV COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION Article 354 paragraph (1) in the implementation of Regional Government, the Regional Government encourages public participation. In paragraph (2) in encouraging community participation as referred to in paragraph (1), the Regional Government: a. convey information about the implementation of Regional Government to the community; b. encourage community groups and organizations to play an active role in the implementation of Regional Government through community capacity building support; c. develop institutionalization and decision-making mechanisms that enable community groups and organizations to be involved effectively; and / or d. other activities in accordance with statutory provisions. In the content of paragraph (3) community participation as referred to in paragraph (1) includes: a. drafting Regional Regulations and Regional policies that regulate and burden the community; b. planning, budgeting, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating regional development; c. management of Regional assets and / or natural resources; and d. organizing public services.

The aspect of community participation is very important to formulate public policies that are more charged with bottom up because regional regulations must reflect the application of local values that can be used as social capital so that social arrangements can be fully agreed upon together. The aspect of community participation is part of the commitment of the Regional Government to build good governance as contained in the content of the principles of good governance.

Along with the legal development concept which is basically constructed as a basis for the Regional Government, it still refers to the value structure that has been formulated through the Republic of Indonesia Act Number 12 of 2011 on the Establishment of Legislation, reminding lawmakers to always pay attention to the principle of the formation of good laws and principles of material content. In establishing legislation, it must be done based on the Principle of Establishing a good Legislation, which includes: 1) "**principle of clarity of purpose**", namely that every Establishment of Legislation must have clear objectives to be achieved; 2) "**the right form of institution or official**" that is, every type of legislation must be made by a state institution or an official who forms an authorized statutory regulation, the legislation can be canceled or null and void if made by a state institution or unauthorized official; 3) "**the principle of conformity between types, hierarchies, and**

material content", namely in the Establishment of Legislation, must pay attention to the appropriate material content in accordance with the type and hierarchy of Legislation Regulations; 4) "**principles can be implemented**", namely that every formation of legislation must take into account the effectiveness of the laws and regulations in the community, both philosophically, sociologically, and juridically; 5) "**principle of utility and usefulness**", namely that every statutory regulation is made because it is really needed and useful in regulating the life of the community, nation, and state; 6) "**the principle of clarity of formulation**", namely that each statutory regulation must meet the technical requirements for the preparation of legislation, systematics, choice of words or terms, and legal language that is clear and easy to understand so as not to cause various kinds of interpretations in its implementation; and 7) "**principle of openness**", that in the formulation of legislation starting from planning, drafting, discussing, ratifying or stipulating, and promulgating is transparent and open. Thus, all levels of society have the widest opportunity to provide input in the formation of legislation. -luasnya untuk memberikan masukan dalam pembentukan peraturan perundang-undangan.

Regarding efforts to realize an effective legal system, it is necessary to restructure legal institutions supported by the increasing quality of human resources and cultural awareness and legal awareness, along with the renewal of legal materials that are harmoniously structured without conflict and overlap and the law is continuously updated according to with demands for development of needs (Prenta, 2011). This is consistent with the arguments of Sutrisno and Sudarminto (2017) who stated:

Sectors of life governed by the rule of law must be able to reach the point of order and a sense of justice, including economic management, human resources and natural resources in order to achieve happiness together.

It needs to be realized that to create legal justice requires an active role from various parties ranging from the formation of legal products to the enforcement of legal products (Bureni, 2013). This is fully realized considering that so far the development of law in this country has tended to move in an artificial and directionless space (Dayanto, 2013). Sutrisno (2015) states that:

Indonesia today is faced with a very "unique" problem of law performance regarding the formal truth treated as the most dominant consideration of legal decision embracing Reine Rechtslehre Kelsenian's way of thinking. An approach that is still in further discussion through a more holistic alternative paradigm.

This is related to the doctrine of legal positivism that is monistic, which only recognizes one kind of justice, namely justice born from positive law (Artadi, 2011).

The entire product of legal norms that have been built by the Regional Government of Sambas Regency must be thoroughly studied integrated with national regulations. This is important considering the condition of the geographical strategic position of the region in the international context, which is bordering land and sea with the country of Malaysia, traversed by the Indonesian archipelago sea lanes and close to Singapore and Batam which are centers of industrial activities and services in ASEAN. Sambas Regency occupies 4.36% of the total area of West Kalimantan Province. Sambas Regency is directly adjacent to Serawak and Natuna Sea in the north and borders with Bengkayang Regency and Singkawang City in the south. While in the West it is directly adjacent to the Natuna Sea and in the east it is bordered by Bengkayang and Serawak Districts. Sambas Regency is one of the regions that contributed to the history of Indonesia through the attachment of the name Sambas to the royal name. As a kingdom, the Sambas Sultanate has a wide area and carries a history of progress, especially in the fields of religion, customs, culture and science.

Although Sambas Regency is one of the districts that has a high historical value but still has obstacles in carrying out development. These obstacles are urgent targets that must be resolved immediately such as improving the quality of human resources, expanding employment, reducing poverty, providing infrastructure, and equitable development. Strategic steps to complete the above targets are then regulated in the Sambas Regional Long Term Development Plan (RPJPD) for 2005-2025 and implemented in stages through the realization of the Sambas Medium-Term Plan (RPJMD) Program for 2012-2016.

The phenomenon of the enactment of product legal norms in the Regional Government of Sambas in the form of Regional Regulations (Perda) which is further highlighted by efforts to inventory other regulations with the contents of local wisdom values to develop the concept of sustainable development in the Sambas Regency area, because the study area on the border is certain have distinctiveness and uniqueness that is not found in other regions that are not border areas with other countries. The social processes that occur in the community in the border region, especially the border with Malaysia, can be used as a preliminary picture to formulate a value policy in the region.

The roles and functions of executive and legislative institutions are faced with the challenge of responding to the community needs of the border region which is then poured through responsive, creative and anticipatory Regional Regulation (PERDA) products along with the development and dynamics of social change in the Malaysian border. This is very reasonable because the Government should be fully oriented towards development based on local resources such as agriculture, forestry, marine and fisheries, many countries that have these resources are now trying to rebuild the development paradigm by giving more attention to the marine sectors, fisheries and agriculture, this reality should be pursued by Indonesia by reviewing sectors based on

natural resources. The seriousness of the government in rearranging development policies based on local resources is expected to be able to realize prosperity for the community as a target community of policy objectives, which in turn is a parameter of the success of development in the sector.

Viewed from a geographical point of view, the majority of Sambas residents work in agriculture, plantation, animal farm, fisheries and forestry. However, the sector has not been managed optimally. Based on data from the Sambas Central Bureau of Statistics, the Sambas Regency Planting Index is still below the 200 Planting Index. While in the plantation sector several types of plantation production such as rubber, coconut, pepper, coffee, cocoa and sugar cane have decreased plantation area and temporary plantation production from oil palm continues to increase in terms of plantation area and palm oil production. Thus it can be concluded that the majority of plantations that dominate the Sambas Regency area are oil palm plantations.

In addition to information on plantation development in order to increase economic growth in Sambas District, through the forestry sector, the Sambas Regional Government seeks to organize the Sambas forest to meet future development needs. However, in the management of forest maintenance, problems were still found such as there are still many forest areas that have not been arranged by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry which have caused difficulties in monitoring, protecting and fostering forest areas to avoid damage and illegal forestry activities. In addition, there are still many non-forestry activities operating in the mangrove forests which cause coastal abrasion and reduced mangrove forest land. Good forest management is one of the indexes for achieving forest ecology management if managed properly based on the application of sustainable development.

Based on some of the descriptions above, the concept of sustainable development is aimed at physical development that is able to prosper the people in order to alleviate the poverty of the border population through improving the natural resource management sector. The management will be a complete and holistic combination of development if it is prepared by taking into account the sustainability of ecology and development in accordance with the Sambas District Spatial Planning (RTRW). Thus in the preparation of the Spatial Planning and Regional Planning must pay attention to aspects: 1) the development of provincial problems and the results of the assessment of the implications of district spatial planning; 2) efforts to promote development and economic growth in the district; 3) alignment of district development aspirations; 4) environmental support and carrying capacity; 5) regional long-term development plan; 6) the spatial plan of the adjacent regency area; and 7) district strategic area spatial plans.

The concept of management and structuring of the Spatial Plan is in fact not running optimally considering that data is still found related to poverty that keeps changing up and down from 2010 to 2014. Based on a study of data from the Central Kalimantan Provincial Bureau of West Kalimantan, specifically in Sambas Regency the percentage of poor people reaches 9.46% or around 42.26 thousand residents in 2014. The data places Sambas Regency as the third most poor area after Ketapang Regency and Landak Regency. In addition to the poverty rate, in terms of aspects of the Human Development Index (HDI) in Sambas Regency classified as unstable because of a decline from 2014 to 2015 from 66.81% in 2013 fell to 63.28% in 2014 and finally stopped at the figure of 64.14% in 2015. The decline in achievement of poverty reduction and the Human Development Index shows that the level of welfare of the population of Sambas is minimal.

Real effort is needed to contribute praxis thinking to the interests of stakeholders in the region, especially policy holders namely bureaucratic apparatus both on the executive (regents and ranks) and legislatures (Regency / City DPRD) so that they can be used as valid reference material in the formulation of value-based regional regulations -The value of local wisdom in an effort to develop sustainable strategies in the border region communities as an alternative to overcome poverty in the border region communities.

This is due to the condition of the welfare of the border communities that need more attention, because in some reasons the argument for the level of welfare can be determined based on the Government's management of the potential of Natural Resources and Human Resources in Sambas District. The form of management is outlined in the form of Government policies to determine the progress of the Sambas area in the coming period. The chosen policy will certainly have an impact on the determination of public policy as outlined in the Regional Regulation of Sambas Regency as a form of regional governance in Sambas Regency.

Local governments must play a maximum role in managing governance that promotes good governance in the end, the policy of the Regional Government that is fully built is able to side with the interests of the community to build prosperity and on the other hand the alignment of wisdom in the environment is not neglected. The formulation of regional policies embodied in the form of Regional Regulations (PERDA) reflects the establishment of good governance values as well as the content of their principles. Local governance must still be based on the existence of local wisdom in the midst of the community.

The study focused more on Sambas Regency because in the review of its strategic area according to the Sambas Regency RTRW in 2015-2035, which was seen from four angles of interest: 1) **Economy** namely Sambas Urban Area; State Border Area; KUAT Pemangkat, Tebas and Galing; Minapolitan area Cultivation and capture; Semparuk Industrial Zone; 2) **Socio-Culture**, namely the Water Front City Region and Sambas Sultanate Complex; Tourism Area of Lake Sebedang, Temajuk Beach and Batu Bejamban (Paloh District); Putri

Serai Beach Tourism Area, Tanjung Batu and Sinam Beach; Meramap Riam and Sambas Botanical Gardens; 3) **Utilization of Natural Resources / High Technology**, namely the Special Terminal and Tanjung Api industrial area in Paloh District; Kota Terpadu Mandiri (KTM) Mas Perkasa Sebunga Gate with hinterland in Paloh District, Galing and Sejangkung; and 4) **Function and carrying capacity of the environment**, namely the Tanjung Belimbing ecosystem area in Paloh District; Bentarang Mountain ecosystem area in Sajingan Besar District.

In addition to being guided by good governance in administering governance and formulating policies to become the public policy of Sambas Regency, the Regional Government of Sambas Regency must pay attention to the local wisdom or socio-culture that grows in the community. Sambas Regency is known as an area that has Malay Muslim culture because Sambas was once an area of the Islamic Empire. The development of Malay Islamic culture in Sambas District was spearheaded by the Sambas Kingdom which gained influence in the Malay region (Malacca) which was oriented to maritime-based life, in contrast to Sampit which was known as land-based. The kingdom of Sambas has a major influence on the meaning of religion as a basis in life and behavior. The Islamic culture that was held firmly by the Sambas residents became a sign for the Sambas Regional Government, which in the preparation of all public policies must prioritize Islamic religious values (Sunandar, 2015).

Social-existing conditions in the border communities, especially Sambas Regency in West Kalimantan require harmony and harmonization of the legal order to be built, bearing in mind that the principle of the rule of law requires a legal system. The necessity for a legal order is a principle that must first be in the state of law.

Harmonization of the law seeks to create harmony, suitability, congruity, compatibility and balance between existing legal norms, to regulate certain fields in people's lives. Harmonization of law as one of the prerequisites to lead to legal development that better meets the needs and interests that develop in the community.

The area on the border, which is unique enough to be important as a study material, considering the application of local wisdom values of local communities with the tendency of the strength of social structures and local culture can be used as the most basic reference in establishing regional policies in the form of locality law products, namely Regional Regulations (PERDA) who are responsive in accommodating the interests and issues that exist in the border community in order to lead to efforts to realize a sustainable development strategy which in the end interests the community's welfare by not ignoring the interests of the environment, products of the Regional Regulation (PERDA) with a biocentric and ecocentric approach.

This understanding is important based on the very basic developments in carrying out the issue of the spirit of Regional Autonomy which is often out of control by ignoring aspects of the preservation of the natural environment. A promising virtue from studies offered through research in partnership with Sambas Regency, the output can be used as a reference model in formulating regional policies in the form of Regional Regulations (PERDA) based on biocentric and ecocentric approaches, in border areas with other countries neighboring Indonesia considering in several preliminary studies it was found that regional legal products that lead to economic aspects, exploitation in the name of increasing Regional Original Income (PAD), ignores the dimension of sustainable development. This condition is a consideration of the superiority of the study in this study, the model of public policy formulation in the border areas of Sambas Regency is finally able to overcome the scarcity of research approaches that lead to building policy formulations with approaches to environmental law, state administration concerning governance in the region and economic interests building community welfare.

Local Government governance that leads to the concept of good governance is a promising bet, by touching on the dimensions of building government policies that contain biocentric and ecocentric values as a fundamental basis for incorporating these issues into formulas providing alternative sustainable development strategies.

Conclusion

Management of border areas, especially in Sambas Regency, must be built based on the concept of integrated border area management so that there is no conflict of interests and authority between agencies considering that infrastructure and physical development policies must be balanced with development in the economic dimension to develop the level of welfare of border communities.

Thus, the formulation of policies developed by the Regional Government in the form of product regulations at the local level, namely the Regional Regulations (PERDA) in Sambas Regency must be more responsive and progressive by involving border community participation so that normalized local values can be obtained positive legal form.

This policy formulation and strategy aims to ensure that the governance of the Regional Government of Sambas Regency must be able to create a clean and transparent government and be accountable for the public interest of the border community, so that the technical regulations formulated at the local level are an elaboration of national regulatory legislation products.

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